

Do heuristics matter for financial literacy? The impact of better heuristics awareness to financial literacy

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Summary

1. Traditional financial education significantly improves students' financial literacy, making it a reliable approach for teaching core financial concepts.
2. The inclusion of heuristics in financial education introduces unnecessary complexity, which can diminish the overall effectiveness of traditional financial education methods.
3. Heuristics awareness can be a double-edged sword, since it may confuse decision-making.
4. Together with traditional methods, policy should focus on interactive approaches for financial education, enabling students to learn in practice.

1. Introduction

Insufficient financial literacy leads individuals to make poor financial choices, resulting in negative outcomes like excessive debt, bankruptcy, and financial instability, perpetuating poverty due to a lack of knowledge and skills in managing personal finances effectively (Mitchell and Lusardi, 2015). Without adequate financial understanding, people become vulnerable to exploitative lending practices, high-interest loans, and fraud, trapping them in cycles of debt and limiting their financial autonomy (Khan et al., 2022). In an increasingly complex financial world, consumers often rely on heuristics—mental shortcuts that facilitate quick decision-making but can lead to errors

(Bernheim, 1995). Therefore, finding effective methods to improve financial literacy and examining whether educating individuals about heuristics can enhance their financial decision-making have become essential (Lusardi, 2019).

While financial education has emerged as the most effective approach to enhancing financial literacy, its long-term impact on financial outcomes and overall well-being remains uncertain (Kaiser et al., 2022). Recent advancements highlight the role of behavioural and cognitive factors in shaping financial literacy, suggesting that behavioural-based financial education can improve understanding by teaching how to make good financial decisions and recognizing factors that impede them (Compen et al., 2022; Pitthan & De Witte, 2022). However,

heuristics present a dual challenge: they can both simplify decision-making and undermine it in complex scenarios (Gigerenzer & Gaissmaier, 2011).

This policy brief summarizes a randomized controlled trial with Flemish (northern Belgian region) secondary school students (Pitthan & De Witte, 2024). We found that traditional financial education improved financial literacy, whereas courses including heuristic content did not. Teaching about heuristics may confuse students by emphasizing both their benefits and drawbacks, making decisions more complex and potentially worsening financial literacy outcomes.

2. Theory and methods

The literature suggests causal links among financial education, financial literacy, and financial outcomes, while recently proposing the relevance of behavioural biases in this causal framework (Carpena & Zia, 2020; Pitthan & De Witte, 2022). Recognizing that heuristics influence financial decisions, we hypothesize that integrating heuristics into financial education could enhance financial literacy and financial outcomes by increasing individuals' awareness of their decision-making processes. On Figure 1, we propose that behavioural-based financial education courses including content about heuristics would make individuals more conscious of their financial decisions, thereby improving financial literacy and outcomes.

To test this, we conducted an experiment with secondary school students aged 14–19 in Flanders, Belgium. The students were randomized into three groups: a control group receiving no course until the experiment's end; a treatment group

receiving traditional financial education (TFE) focusing on financial knowledge concepts; and a treatment group receiving heuristics financial education (HFE), which included behavioural-based material on availability and gambler's fallacy heuristics in addition to the core financial content. All participants completed pre- and post-tests assessing financial literacy and heuristics awareness. Using OLS estimates and causal mediation analysis, we evaluated the effects of the treatments on financial literacy by means of the randomized controlled trial design to identify causal relationships.

3. Results

Our study assessed the impact of traditional financial education versus heuristics education on students' financial literacy, and found that traditional financial education significantly improved financial literacy scores, while the same did not happen for heuristics education. This suggests that introducing heuristics education may complicate decision-making processes, potentially causing confusion or distraction that hinders the acquisition of financial literacy.

Additionally, students who received traditional financial education exhibited a significant increase in heuristics-based behaviour. This implies that enhancing financial knowledge without addressing heuristics may lead to overconfidence and a greater reliance on mental shortcuts in decision-making. Mediation analysis showed no significant indirect effect of heuristics education on financial literacy through increased awareness of heuristics. These findings indicate that while traditional financial education effectively boosts financial knowledge, incorporating heuristics education requires careful integration to avoid

unintended negative impacts on students' decision-making processes.

4. Policy implications

Our findings suggest that including heuristics in financial education programs for secondary school students may not be advisable, as it can diminish the effectiveness of traditional financial education. Teaching about heuristics appears to overcomplicate decision-making processes, leading to information overload and diverting attention from essential financial concepts. This makes financial decisions more complex than necessary without enhancing financial literacy. Policymakers should therefore reconsider the inclusion of heuristics in financial education curricula for young students.

Instead, policies aiming to improve financial literacy should focus on proven traditional education methods and prioritize interactive, practical approaches such as "learning by doing" to mitigate the negative effects of heuristics. Engaging students in practical exercises allows them to experience firsthand the advantages and disadvantages of heuristics, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of their implications. Future policy initiatives should also consider conducting longer-term studies across diverse contexts to ensure the sustainability and generalizability of educational interventions. Furthermore, behavioural insights can also be essential to discover new ways in which financial education can help students to achieve better financial literacy and become more independent decision-makers (Pitthan & De Witte, 2024).

If we stretch the findings beyond financial literacy, several broader policy implications can be drawn from our study.

First, policymakers should consider the cognitive load on students when designing educational interventions. The finding that heuristics education can complicate decision-making highlights the importance of ensuring that educational programs are not overly complex, particularly for younger learners. This implies that educational policy should prioritize simplicity and clarity in curricula, avoiding the introduction of concepts that may overwhelm students and hinder learning outcomes. By focusing on cognitive accessibility, education systems can ensure that students are better equipped to retain and apply the knowledge they acquire.

Second, the study points to the importance of long-term evaluations of educational interventions. As short-term studies may fail to capture the full impact of an educational approach, policymakers should support longitudinal research that tracks the outcomes of (financial) education over time. This can help to identify not only the immediate effects of different teaching methods but also their long-term implications. By investing in sustained research and evaluation, policymakers can ensure that educational reforms are based on evidence that reflects the enduring benefits and potential drawbacks of specific teaching methods.

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Figures

Fig. 1. Causal relationships of behavioural-based financial education.

Source: Pitthan, F. & De Witte, K. (2024)

Further Information:

Pitthan, F. & De Witte, K. (2024). Do heuristics matter for financial literacy? The impact of better heuristics awareness to financial literacy. *Finance Research Letters*. In Press.

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